

Title: Distribution of alternative untranslated regions within the mRNA of the *CELF1* splicing factor affects its expression

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Fig. 1C

Description of Figure 1C: RT-PCR analysis of alternative splicing of *CELF1* 5'UTR in skeletal muscle samples of non-DM and DM1 patients (left panel: primers 5_F1 and 5_R; right panel: primers 5_F2 and 5_R). The splicing in this region of mRNAs transcribed from P1 (left panel) or P2 (right panel) is disrupted. In both cases, the shortest isoform (i1) lacking alternative cassette exons predominates ($P = 0.02$ for P1 and $P = 0.003$ for P2, t test), while isoform 5 (i5) containing ex5 (AUG1) is less prevalent. Framed gels are presented.

The unprocessed, full- sized images cannot be provided due to storage server damage. It was not possible to repeat these reactions due to limited amount of patients cDNA, therefore primers specificity in human skeletal muscles is shown.

Corresponding to Figures: 1C, 1F, 2B

Specificity of primers used in the reactions presented in Fig. 1c, 1f and 2b in human skeletal muscles.

(a) Gel, specificity of primers used to amplification of *CELF1* 5'UTR isoforms transcribed from the promoter 1 (5_F1 and 5_R) corresponding to Fig. 1c, left panel and 2b, upper panel; specificity of primers used to amplification of *CELF1* 5'UTR isoforms transcribed from the promoter 2 (5_F2 and 5_R) corresponding to Fig. 1c, right panel and 2b, lower panel; specificity of primers used to amplification of *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms *a*, *d* and *c* (3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) corresponding to Fig. 1f, left panel; specificity of primers used to amplification of *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms *a*, *d* and *c* (3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) corresponding to Fig. 1f, right panel.

(b) The same gel which is presented in (a). Gel is cropped to indicate *CELF1* UTRs isoforms.

Expected products sizes:

primers 5_F1 + 5_R: *i1-P1*, 273 bp; *i2-P1*, 313 bp; *i3-P1*, 385 bp; *i4-P1*, 384 bp; *i5-P1*, 537 bp;

primers 5_F2 + R_5: *i1-P2*, 288 bp; *i2-P2*, 328 bp; *i3-P2*, 400 bp; *i5-P2*, 552 bp;

primers 3_F1 + 3_Ra: isoform *a*, 475 bp;

primers 3_F1 + 3_Rcd: isoform *c*, 335 bp; isoform *d* 423 bp;

primers 3_F1 + 3_Rb: isoform *b*, 393 bp.

All PCR products were sequenced to confirm their sequences.

Gel edges are indicated with arrows. Wells are indicated. SkM, human skeletal muscles in three biological replicates. Total RNA was obtained from the undefined skeletal muscles (BioChain Inc.). Red rectangle, similar areas from the original gels were used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig. 1F

Description of Figure 1F: RT-PCR analysis of CELF1 3'UTR isoforms distribution in DM1 skeletal muscles (left panel: primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd; right panel: primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rb). Framed gels are presented.

The unprocessed, full-sized images cannot be provided due to storage server damage (the same as in 1C).

Fig. 1G

Description of Figure 1G: The expression of CELF1 is under the control of MBNLs. Knockdown of MBNL1 and MBNL2 has no effect on CELF1 mRNA level (normalized to GAPDH); although, decreases the inclusion of ex5 (real-time RT-PCR; primers 5_F3 and 5_R1, normalized to all CELF1 transcripts) (siCtrl, n = 5; siMBNL1&2#1, n = 5). The distributions of CELF1 3'UTR isoforms are sensitive to MBNL protein level (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) (n = 3). CELF1 protein (normalized to GAPDH) is upregulated in MBNLs deficiency conditions (siCtrl, n = 6; siMBNL1&2#1, n = 6). The efficiency of MBNL1 and MBNL2 knockdown is presented in Supplementary Fig. S2c.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Fig. 1G.

a. middle panel; CELF1 3'UTR isoforms

b. right panel; anti-CELF1

c. right panel; anti-GAPDH

(a) Gel, *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #1.

(b, c) Western blots, *CELF1* (b) and *GAPDH* (c) as loading control after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #1. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig.2B

Description of Figure 2B: Splicing profiles of CELF1 5'UTR during skeletal muscle development (F, fetal; A, adult) and in adult heart and brain tissue (A, adult) (upper panel: primers 5_F1 and 5_R; lower panel: primers 5_F2 and 5_R). The expression of i5-P1 (upper panel) and i5-P2 (lower panel) is the highest in adult skeletal muscles and is very low (i5-P1) or undetectable (i5-P2) in the adult brain. An unspecific RT-PCR product is marked with #; cropped gels are presented.

The unprocessed, full-sized images cannot be provided due to storage server damage (the same as in 1C and 1F).

Fig.2D

Description of Figure 2D: RT-PCR analysis of Celf1 3'UTR isoforms in mouse skeletal muscles (n = 4), heart (n = 4) and brain (n = 4) during the development in 1 and 90 days after birth (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd). Cropped gels are presented.

Full size images corresponding to Fig. 2D.

Figure 2d

Upper and lower panels: Gels, *Celf1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification in mouse tissues. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig.3E

Description of Figure 3E: The transfection with the same amount of plasmid encoding CELF1-AUG1 and CELF1-AUG2 results in the same quantity of translated proteins. Quantification of the level of CELF1-Myc-tag is normalized to GAPDH (COS-7 cells, n = 3).

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Fig. 3e.

(a) Western blot, CELF1-Myc.

(b) Western blots, GAPDH as loading control.

Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig.3F

Description of Figure 3F: Splicing activity of CELF1 isoforms. Different amounts of CELF1-AUG1 or CELF1-AUG2 expression construct were cotransfected with NF1 and cTNT splicing minigenes containing CELF-dependent alternative ex23a and ex5, respectively. The results of RT-PCR splicing assays showed that CELF1-AUG2 (the shorter isoform) had lower splicing activity than CELF1-AUG1 (COS-7 cells, n = 3 biological replicates). The lower panels show the CELF1 binding site in intronic region of regulated minigenes.

Full size images corresponding to Fig. 3F.

Gels, alternative splicing of NF1 ex23a (upper panel) and cTNT ex5 (lower panel) after CELF1-AUG1-Myc and CELF1-AUG2-Myc overexpression. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig.4C

Description of Figure 4C: The distributions of CELF1 3'UTR isoforms are sensitive to CELF activity (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) (GFP and CELF1, n = 3; siCtrl, n = 6; siCEL1#1, n = 5).

Full size images corresponding to Fig. 4C.

Gels, *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification after GFP-*CELF1* overexpression (left panel) and *CELF1* knock-down with siRNA set #1 (right panel). Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Fig.4E

Description of Figure 4E: Level of Celf1 protein in different murine tissues. 10 µg of protein were loaded per lane. Vinculin was used as a loading control for samples from the same tissue. The total protein is a loading control for samples from different tissues. M molecular weight marker.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Fig. 4E.

a. anti-CELF1

b. anti-Vinculin

c. staining with SimplyBlue SafeStain

(a, b) Western blots, Celf1 (a) and Vinculin (b) as loading control in mouse tissues. (c) Gel, total protein from mouse tissues stained with SimplyBlue SafeStain. Original images (left panel) and high

contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane or gel edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Supplementary Figure S2.

Description of Fig.S2: Impact of MBNLs on CELF1 5'UTR and 3'UTR isoforms distribution.

(a) Overexpression of GFP-MBNL1-43 induces the inclusion of *CELF1* ex5 ($n = 3$) and knockdown of MBNL1 and MBNL2 decreases the inclusion of this exon ($n = 3$) (primers 5_F3, 5_F4 and 5_R1). Cropped gels are presented. GFP-MBNL1-43 level after overexpression in HeLa cells was published previously¹.

(b) *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms α is upregulated after MBNL1 overexpression (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) ($n = 3$). Cropped gels are presented.

(c) Levels of MBNL1 and MBNL2 normalised to GAPDH after knockdown with siRNA set#1 in HSkM and HeLa cells. Framed blots are presented.

(d) Knockdown of MBNL1 and MBNL2 with other siRNA set decreases the inclusion of *CELF1* ex5 in HepG2 cells (siCtrl, $n = 6$; siMBNL1&2#2, $n = 5$) (primers 5_F3, 5_F4 and 5_R1). *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms α is downregulated after MBNL1 and MBNL2 knockdown with other siRNA set (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) (siCtrl, $n = 6$; siMBNL1&2#2, $n = 4$). *CELF1* protein is upregulated after MBNLs knockdown with second siRNA set in HepG2 cells (siCtrl, $n = 3$; siMBNL1&2#2, $n = 6$); Cropped gels are presented.

(e) Levels of MBNL1 and MBNL2 normalised to Vinculin after knockdown with siRNA set#2 in HepG2 cells. Framed blots are presented.

Full size images corresponding to Supplementary Fig S2a and S2b.

Gels, *CELF1* 5'UTR isoforms amplification after GFP-MBNL1 overexpression (left, upper panel) and *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #1 (right, upper panel) and *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification after GFP-MBNL1 overexpression (lower panel). Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S2c left panel.

Supplementary Figure S2c left panel

a. anti-MBNL1

b. anti-MBNL2

c. anti-GAPDH

Western blots, MBNL1 (a), MBML2 (b) and GAPDH (c) as loading control after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #1 in HSkM cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S2c right panel.

Supplementary Figure S2c right panel

a. anti-MBNL1

b. anti-MBNL2

c. anti-GAPDH

Western blots, MBNL1 (a), MBML2 (b) and GAPDH (c) as loading control after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #1 in HeLa cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images corresponding to Supplementary Fig S2d left and middle panels.

Supplementary Figure S2d

left panel

middle panel

Gels, *CELF1* 5'UTR and 3'UTR isoforms amplification after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #2 in HepG2 cells. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S2d right panel.

Supplementary Figure S2d right panel

a. anti-CELF1

b. anti-Vinculin

Western blots, CELF1 and Vinculin (d) as loading control after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #2 in HepG2 cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S2e.

Supplementary Figure S2e

a. anti-MBNL1

b. anti-MBNL2

c. anti-Vinculin

Western blots, MBNL1 (a), MBML2 (b) and Vinculin (c) as loading control after *MBNL1* and *MBNL2* knock-down with siRNA set #2 in HepG2 cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images

(right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Supplementary Figure S3B

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S3b.

Supplementary Figure S3b

a. anti-CELF1

b. anti-Vinculin

Western blots with anti-CELF1 antibody (a) and anti-Vinculin (b) as loading control. Original images (upper panels) and high contrasted images (lower panels) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Supplementary Figure S4

Description of Fig. S4: Levels of *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms under miRNA deficiency conditions.

(a) Real-time RT-PCR for *CELF1* mRNA level (normalised to *GAPDH*) and RT-PCR for *CELF1* 3'UTR isoform *a* level (normalised to *CELF1*) (primers 3_F1 and 3_Ra) in HSkM cells after *DROSHA* and *DGCR8* knockdown ($n = 3$). A cropped gel is presented on the right panel.

(b) Overexpression of GFP-CELF1 in HepG2 cells. Framed blots are presented.

(c) Level of CELF1 normalised to Vinculin after knockdown with siRNA set#1 in HepG2 cells ($n = 6$). Framed blots are presented.

(d) The distributions of *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms are sensitive to CELF1 activity after siRNA set#2 (primers 3_F1, 3_Ra and 3_Rcd) (siCtrl, $n = 6$; siCELF1#2, $n = 5$). Level of CELF1 normalised to Vinculin after knockdown with siRNA set#2 in HepG2 cells (siCtrl, $n = 6$; siCELF1#2, $n = 4$). Cropped gels are presented.

(e) Ct values of *Celf1* cDNA after amplification with RT-qPCR in mouse tissues. To cDNA synthesis were used 500 ng of total RNA.

Full size image corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S4a.

Supplementary Figure S4a

Gel, *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification after DROSHA and DGCR8 knock-down. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S4b.

Supplementary Figure S4b

Western blots with anti-CELF1 antibody and anti-GAPDH as loading control. Original images (upper panel) and high contrasted images (lower panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows; some edges are not visible due to short exposure time. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S4c.

Supplementary Figure S4c

a. anti-CELF1

b. anti-Vinculin

Western blots, CELF1 (a) and Vinculin (b) as loading control after *CELF1* knock-down with siRNA set #1 in HepG2 cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.

Full size images of the blot corresponding to Supplementary Fig. S4d.

Supplementary Figure S4d

a. left panel

b. right panel; anti-CELF1

c. right panel; anti-Vinculin

(a) Gels, *CELF1* 3'UTR isoforms amplification after *CELF1* knock-down with siRNA set #2 in HepG2 cells.

(b, c) Western blots, CELF1 (b) and Vinculin (c) as loading control after *CELF1* knock-down with siRNA set #2 in HepG2 cells. Original images (left panel) and high contrasted images (right panel) are presented; membrane edges are indicated with arrows. Red rectangle, bands used to make the manuscript figures.